

SERVICE QUALITY MANAGEMENT PRACTICE AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF FOOD, BEVERAGE AND TOBACCO MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN SOUTH EAST, NIGERIA

Okolie, Jonathan Ibekwe (Ph.D.)

Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, ESUT

Email: Jonalbva1020@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13890787>

Abstract: The last decade has witnessed an increase in the acceptance and use of service quality management practices even in the manufacturing industry because service quality is a way of assuring customers of best services. The recent challenge faced by most manufacturing firms in Nigeria is how to adopt a strategy for high-quality services that would satisfy the needs of the customers at a reduced and effective price and still ensure that they remained in business without any incurrence of debt. The study evaluated service quality management practice and customer satisfaction of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives were to: assess relationship between level of reliability of service quality and the customer satisfaction score; ascertain relationship between responsiveness of service quality and the net promoter score of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. The population of study was five thousand, five hundred and eighty-four (5584) employees of manufacturing firm under study in South East Nigeria. The sample size of 359 was established using Ferund and William statistical formula at 5 percent error margin. A survey design was adopted for the study. Instrument used for data collection was structured questionnaire. Two hundred and ninety-seven (297) copies of the questionnaire were returned. Z - test was used to test the hypotheses. The findings indicated that there was significant positive relationship between the level of reliability of service quality and the customer satisfaction score $Z(95, n = 297) = 6.600$ to $8.283, p < .05$. There was significant positive relationship between the responsiveness of service quality and the net promoter score $Z(95, n = 297) = 7.993$ to $9.096, p < .05$. The study concluded that the level of reliability of service quality, responsiveness of service quality had significant positive relationship with customer satisfaction score, net promoter score of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that managers should ensure that there existed underpinning ethos in regards to the reliability that guided organizational activities as it would help retain customers and boost organizational performance and food and beverage firms should strive to improve service responsiveness if at all they wanted to satisfy their customers, which ultimately would be reflected in higher profitability.

Keywords: service quality management practice, customer satisfaction, reliability and responsiveness, customer score and net promoter score.

INTRODUCTION

The last decade has witnessed an increase in the acceptance and use of service quality management even in the manufacturing industry, with service quality being an important factor for growth, survival and success of firms. Measuring the quality of service outputs is often more difficult than measuring the quality of a good, because services are abstract rather than concrete, transient rather than permanent, and psychological rather than physical (Sumarjan & Arendt, 2016).

The fact that it is now well understood that the fabrication of products is quite different from delivery of services, the concept of Service Quality management has gained increased attention. It aims at providing quality service to ensure customers' satisfaction (Al Manhaway, 2014). Customers are faced with an unprecedented range of choices, not only choices of what to buy but where to buy it. Service quality is judged by what a customer perceives rather than what a provider offers. In order to ensure that customers are highly satisfied and loyal customers retained, organizations throughout the world are striving to produce products and services of superior quality (Pattanayak & Maddulety, 2018).

Customer satisfaction is simply a function of the difference between perceived performance and expectation; it is the overall customer attitude towards a service provider, or an emotional reaction to the difference between what customers anticipate and what they receive. Customers' satisfaction increases customer retention because satisfied customers tend to be less influenced by competitors, less price sensitive and stay loyal longer (Chamchong & Ichon, 2015).

To satisfy the ever increasing customers' expectations, managers need to find cost-effective ways to continuously improve the quality of products and services and shorten response time. This requires trading-off the cost of achieving these improvements and the benefits from higher performance. When companies do not meet customers' expectations, the resultant losses can be substantial. A product or service will be successful in any market at home or overseas if it primarily satisfies consumer's needs. Customer satisfaction is a person's feelings of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product's perceived performance or outcome in relation to his/her expectations (Kotler, 2019).

Organisations are placing increase emphasis on customer satisfaction to enhance customer loyalty to attain customer satisfaction the customer service department must be able to understand and respond to customer needs through provision of high quality service. In modern business philosophy business should be customer oriented and the implementation of the main principles of continuous improvement, justifies the importance of evaluating and analyzing customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is considered as baseline of standardize and excellence of performance for many business. It also helps to identify the potential market opportunities (Evangelos and Yannis, 2015). This study therefore is necessary to evaluate the relationship between service quality management (SQM) practice and customer satisfaction of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Consumers and customers often demand changes. These changes further drive the service provisioning and delivery forward, with increasing demand for quality. Since services are intangible in nature their success and

failure is not easily measured or quantified. Thus, the challenge now arises as to how companies in the manufacturing industry will meet such client demands, particularly in a time of extensive competition from numerous bidders. Many other factors, increase problems concerning quality and result in companies cutting corners in an attempt to be more competitive. Sometimes, they also reduce bids by cutting profit margins in the hope of winning the few jobs available. Quality is a major problem in the Nigerian manufacturing industry, where most organisations promise quality in project implementation but fail to meet the required standard and client expectations. Significant amounts of time, money and resources (concerning both human and materials) are wasted every year due to insufficient or non-existent service quality management procedures. This chronic problem is traced to unreliability, unresponsiveness, unusability, little or no assurance of service quality, low productivity, inferior conditions, and inadequate quality management techniques, which mean the standards of quality are not properly managed. This study seeks to address the relationship between service quality management practice and customer satisfaction of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the service quality management practice and customer satisfaction of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives were to:

- i. Assess relationship between the level of reliability of service quality and the customer satisfaction score of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.
- ii. Ascertain relationship between the responsiveness of service quality and the net promoter score of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Service

Service is any activity or benefit that one party can offer to another, which is essentially intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything. Its production may or may not be tied to a physical product (Jashaliya, 2020).

Quality

Quality is defined as a process that "should be aimed at the needs of the customer, present and future" (Demirbag, Tatoglu, Tekinkus & Zaim 2016). Furthermore, Philip (2015) defined quality as, "conformance to requirements, not as goodness" quality means "meeting the customer's requirements".

Management

Management is a social process which is designed to ensure the cooperation, participation, intervention and involvement of others in the effective achievement of a given or pre-determined goal or objective. The term management is derived from an Italian word "maneggiare" which means to "train horses" or literally "to handle". From the French word "maneger", it means to economize and manage an act of guiding or leading. Etymologically therefore, it means to handle, direct, economically guide and lead (Amadi, 2018).

Service Quality Management

Melaku (2015) defines services as any act or performance that one party can offer to another that is essentially intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything, its production may not be tied to a physical product.

Reliability of Service Quality

Studies of Lam (2015) ranked reliability as first in the dimensions of the service quality model. This is defined as the ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately” or “delivering on its promises. “Getting it right first time all the time” became the bull's eye for keeping promises, providing timely and accurate information to customers and meeting deadlines.

Responsiveness of Service Quality

Pehrsson, (2015) described customer responsiveness as how the organisation involve customers in their decision making in value addition activities like solving customers’ problems, building relationships, and customizing service offering. In this context the organisation respond to the customer needs.

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or surpass customer expectation. Customer satisfaction is defined as "the number of customers, or percentage of total customers, whose reported experience with a firm, its products, or its services (ratings) exceeds specified satisfaction goals. It is seen as a key performance indicator within business and is often part of a Balanced Scorecard (Farris, Neil, Bendle, Pfeifer and David, 2015). *Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT)* measures customer satisfaction with a business, purchase, or interaction. It's one of the most straightforward ways to measure customer satisfaction (Alex, 2022). Customer satisfaction score (often abbreviated as CSAT) is a term frequently used in marketing. It is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or surpass customer expectation. A *net promoter score* is a method of using a single survey question to gauge customer satisfaction with a product. The Net Promoter Score (NPS) is one of the most important metrics of brand health, and identifying customers who would or would not recommend company brand (Kibucha, 2021).

Theoretical Framework

But significantly the study was anchored on SERVQUAL theory because it has contend independent variables. SERVQUAL model was conceived by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1985). The SERVQUAL model is a multiple- item measure that can be used to identify and deduce customer perceptions and service expectations. It is considered to be reliable and valid for evaluating service quality in a number of industries. To develop the SERVQUAL scale, Parasuraman *et al.* (1985) gathered empirical data from five different service industries: appliance renovation and maintenance companies, retail banking, long distance telephone, security, brokerage, and credit cards. The SERVQUAL model initially acknowledged ten dimensions of service quality (tangible, reliability, responsiveness, communication, credibility, security, competence, courtesy, understanding, knowing customers, and access). Subsequently, these ten dimensions were suppressed into five (reliability, responsiveness, tangible, assurance and empathy). The SERVQUAL model hinges on gaps in service quality, which addresses differences in service quality expectations and perceptions. Hutton and Richardson (1995) state

that the broader the gap, the lesser the perception of quality appears in consumer minds, and vice-versa. The SERVQUAL scale has been imitated and appreciated well in the service quality literature in the last decades by academics, researchers and industry people (Buttle, 1996). Hence, SERVQUAL dimensions are adopted in this study to measure the relationship between service quality management practice and customers satisfaction in manufacturing firms.

Empirical Review

Afroz, (2019) examined effect of service quality on customer satisfaction evidence from Banks in Tangail. This study attempts was to determine the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction both from public and private banks in Tangail city. A significant correlation between the performance of promises in time and professions of the clients are observed. Perceived service quality factors have significant relationship with the overall service quality of the banks located in Tangail City which indicates that the service quality dimension have strong influence on the overall customer satisfaction. After all, findings indicate that service quality and all its dimensions have significant and positive association with customer satisfaction.

Chege, (2021) studied examining the influence of service reliability on customer satisfaction in the insurance industry in Kenya. This study examines the influence of service reliability on customer satisfaction in the insurance industry in Kenya. Results were presented in form of tables and path diagrams for the structural equation models. Service reliability was found to have a statistically significant influence on customer satisfaction ($r = 0.840$, $p\text{-value} = 0.027$). The study found that there was a variation of levels of customer satisfaction across entities but this was not attributed to service reliability.

Abdul-Qadir, Abubakar & Utomi, (2021) carried out a study on impact of service quality on customer retention of listed food and beverages companies in Kaduna State. This study examines the effect of service quality on customer retention of listed food and beverages companies in Kaduna State. The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of service quality on customer retention of listed food and beverages companies in Kaduna State. The study used an explanatory research design also known as causal research. The findings of the study show that service quality is positive and significantly associated with the customer retention. It reveals that outcome quality has a t-value of 3.349, coefficient value of 0.471 and a significance value of 0.002.

Ngaliman, & Eka (2019) carried out a study on the effect of tangibles, responsiveness, and reliability on customer satisfaction of delivery services in Indonesia. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of latent tangible variables, responsiveness, and reliability on consumer satisfaction. The results of the study found that tangibles have no direct effect towards consumer satisfaction, responsiveness has a direct effect on consumer satisfaction, reliability, and has a direct effect on consumer satisfaction, tangibles do not have a direct effect on reliability, and responsiveness has a direct effect on reliability.

Gobena, (2019) examined the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction: A case study on nekemte municipality, Oromia region, Ethiopia. The main objective of this study was to assess the overall level of service quality and customer satisfaction in Nekemte Municipality. The findings of the study show that service quality of customer satisfaction is below average, and customers are not satisfied with the service.

Gap in Empirical Review

From the empirical literature review, the study identified conceptual, empirical and contextual knowledge gaps. Conceptually, prior studies have mainly used one or two service quality dimensions and studied their relationship with customer satisfaction (Omar, 2015; Lee, Lee & Dewald, 2016; Pandey & Devasagayam, 2016; Rachman, 2017; Bahadur, Aziz & Zulfiqar, 2018). Some authors found that 3 out of the five dimensions had the most influence on customer satisfaction while other authors who only focused on one dimension found a positive relationship e.g Olakutan and Ojo (2016) and Omar (2015). This implies that this relationship still presents mixed findings warranting further research.

The current study instead employed all the service quality dimensions to establish their relationship with customer satisfaction. Contextually, prior studies were conducted in different environments/ countries that have both social, economic and cultural differences from where the current study will take place, since market dynamics in developing markets like Nigeria differ significantly, that is, how customers perceive quality of a service in Nigeria may differ from how it is perceived in developed markets. Additionally majority of prior studies were conducted in sectors such as e-commerce and banking industry suggesting that manufacturing industry requires more research to be done. This is because the service offering and the customer profiles for the manufacturing industry differ from the industries mentioned. Arising from these conceptual, empirical and contextual knowledge gaps, this study sought to address them by investigating the relationship between service quality management practice and customer satisfaction of manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

In this study we employed survey research design since it involves the examination of phenomenon without any attempt to manipulate the study variables and is characterized by the selection of random samples from population to obtain empirical knowledge of contemporary nature (Andrew, 2018). In the course of conducting this research work, two types of data was collected such as primary and secondary sources of data. The population of this study was made up of management, senior and junior staff of ten selected manufacturing firms in south- East Nigeria registered under Manufacturing Association of Nigeria, (MAN) which gave a total of five thousand, five hundred and eighty four employees (5,584). The study sample size was three hundred and fifty nine (359) respondents. This sample size is justified because the population was huge and such a sample would be sufficient to address the research problem. The data collected were presented and analyzed at two levels, namely descriptive analysis, percentages and Z - test was used for the test of hypotheses. Data from the questionnaire were analyzed with the aid of SPSS version 23 using simple, and percentages. Data from the questionnaire were further analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

There is no Positive Significant Relationship Between the Level of Reliability of Service Quality and the Customer Satisfaction Score of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in South East, Nigeria.

Table 1 One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test: on the relationship between the level of Reliability of Service Quality and the Customer Satisfaction Score of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in South East, Nigeria

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	The goods are of high sales value that attract customer to buy more	The products are always available at any period they are needed	The testability of the products proves its effectiveness to the public	The goods can be maintained and improved	The standard of the products are appreciable
N	297	297	297	297	297
Uniform Parameters ^a ^b	Minimum	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.460	.383	.460	.481
	Positive	.138	.222	.135	.104
	Negative	-.460	-.383	-.460	-.481
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	7.935	6.600	7.935	8.283	7.935
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from 6.600 to 8.283 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as displayed in the table was normally distributed. This affirmed the assertion of the most of the respondents that there was significant relationship between the level of reliability of service

quality and the customer satisfaction score of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from 6.600 to 8.283 against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that there was significant positive relationship between the level of reliability of service quality and the customer satisfaction score of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Test of Hypothesis Two

There is no Positive Significant Relationship Between the Responsiveness of Service Quality and the Net Promotes Score of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 2 One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test: on the Relationship Between the Responsiveness of Service Quality and the Net Promotes Score of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in South East, Nigeria.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	The promote attention to the expectation of the general public enhance attraction of new customers	The social support of the organization to the people encourage buying the products	The choice of the organization in products production is acceptable to the people	Putting empowerment ahead of controlling increases more sale	The basic organization produces supplied to the people promote more productivity	
N	297	297	297	297	297	
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum 1	1	1	1	1	
	Maximum 5	5	5	5	5	
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive	.528	.464	.497	.444	.464
	Negative	.051	.155	.098	.209	.094
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	-.528	-.464	-.497	-.444	-.464	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	9.096	7.993	8.573	7.645	7.993	
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from, 7.993 to 9.096 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as displayed in the table was normally distributed. This affirmed the assertion of the most of the respondents that there was significant positive relationship between the responsiveness of service quality and the net promotes score of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from 7.993 to 9.095 against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that there was significant positive relationship between the responsiveness of service quality and the net promotes score of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

The study made the following findings

- i. There was positive significant relationship between the level of reliability of service quality and the customer satisfaction score of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria $Z(95, n = 297) = 6.600$ to $8.283, p < .05$. This shows that as far as an organization has reliable employees and management customers would be happy to continue business with that organization. This can be observed through referrals made by the satisfied customers
- ii. There was positive significant relationship between the responsiveness of service quality and the net promotes score of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of $Z(95, n = 297) = 7.993$ to $9.096, p < .05$. This shows that when there is quick response of an organization to its clients the more likely the organizations revenue growth is maximized with revenue growth relative to competitors within the industry,

Conclusion

The study concluded that the level of reliability of service quality, responsiveness of service quality, had positive significant relationship with customer satisfaction score, net promotes score, of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms. Customer satisfaction and service quality are considered as a crucial aspect in business; for the development of a company highly depends on how good they maintain their customer through service. Indeed good service quality is expected to result in customer satisfaction, therefore will increase customer's retention and loyalty.

Recommendations

The study recommends that

- i. Managers should ensure that there exists underpinning ethos in regards to the reliability that guides organizational activities as it will help retain customers and boost organization performance. Also

organizations should ensure consistency in business as it is the first art to boost reliability between clients and the organization.

- ii. Organizations must strive to improve service responsiveness if at all they want to satisfy their customers, which ultimately will be reflected in higher profitability.

REFERENCES

- Abdul-Qadir, A.B., Abubakar H.S., & Utomi Q.A.R., (2021) Impact of service quality on customer retention of listed food and beverages companies in Kaduna State. *Gusau International Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 4(1), 1-21
- Al Manhaway, A. (2014). TQM critical success factors in hospitality industry and their impact on customer loyalty: a theoretical model. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*. 4(1), 25-37
- Alex B., (2022). *What is customer satisfaction score (CSAT)?* <https://blog.hubspot.com/service/>
- Amadi, E. (2018). *Introduction to Educational Administration: A Module*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273143560_Introduction_to_Educational_Administration_A_Module/citation/download
- Afroz N.N., (2019). Effect of service quality on customer satisfaction evidence from banks in tangail. *Management Studies and Economic Systems (MSES)*, 4 (2), 145-159
- Andrew, B.M (2018). *Service quality and customer satisfaction in the banking sector in Kenya*
- Bahadur, W., Aziz, S. & Zulfiqar, S. (2018). Effect of employee empathy on customer satisfaction and loyalty during employee customer interactions: The mediating role of customer affective commitment and perceived service quality, *Cogent Business & Management*, 5(1), 5-56
- Chamchong, P., & Ichon, W. (2015). Relationship between customer satisfaction and TQM: A case study in the thai conveniences store. *Journal of Management Science Research*. 22(05), 839-856.
- Chege C.N., (2021). Examining the influence of service reliability on customer satisfaction in the insurance industry in Kenya. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* 10 (1) 2147- 4478)
- Demirbag, M., Tatoglu, E., Tekinkus, M., & Zaim, S. (2016). An analysis of the relationship between TQM implementation and organisational performance: Evidence from Turkish SMEs. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 17(6), 829-847

- Evangelos, G & Yannis, S. (2015). *Customer satisfaction evaluation: methods for measuring and implementing service quality*. London: Springer.
- Farris, P. W.; Neil, T. B; Phillip, E. P. & David, J. R. (2015). *Marketing metrics: The definitive guide to measuring marketing performance*. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Gobena A.G., (2019). The impact of service quality on customer satisfaction: a case study on nekemte municipality, oromia region, ethiopia. *Annals of Social Sciences & Management Studies* 4 (1), 14-24
- Hutton, C. L, Harvey, O. J. & Sherif, M. (1995). Assimilation and contrast effects in reactions to communication and attitude change. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 55(1), 244-52
- Jashaliya, K. (2020). *Service*. Retrieved from <https://www.economicdiscussion.net/marketing-2/service/service/32466>
- Kotler,P., Keller, K. (2019). *Marketing management*. New jersey: Person education.
- Kibucha F., (2021). *Net Promoter score 101: definition, purpose and calculation*
<https://www.geopoll.com/blog/net-promoter-score-101/>
- Lam, T.K.(2015). Making sense of SERVQUAL's dimensions to the Chinese customers in Macau. *J. Market Focused Manag*, 5(1), 43–58.
- Lee, L., Lee, M.J. & Dewald, B. (2016). Measuring the customers' perception of tangible service quality in the restaurant industry: An emphasis on the upscale dining segment, *Journal of Foodservice Business Research*, 19(1), 21-38.
- Melaku M (2015). The impact of service quality, company image and switching barrier on customer retention: mediating role of customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Applied Business and International Management* 4(2), 57-64
- Ngaliman, M. G. & Eka J, S (2019). The effect of tangibles, responsiveness, and reliability on customer satisfaction of delivery services. *SSRG International Journal of Economics and Management Studies* 6(5), 86-92
- Omar, H.F.H. (2015). Determining the influence of the reliability of service quality on customer satisfaction: The case of libyan e-commerce customers. *International Journal of Learning & Development*, 5(1), 1-18

- Olatokun, W. M., & Ojo, F. O. (2016). Influence of service quality on consumers' satisfaction with mobile telecommunication services in Nigeria. *Information Development*, 32(3), 398–408.
- Pandey, S.K. & Devasagayam, R. (2016). Responsiveness as antecedent of satisfaction and referrals in financial services marketing: Empirical evidence from an emergent economy. *The Journal of Applied Business Research*, 28(1), 115-131
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A., & Berry, L.L.(1985). A conceptual model of service quality management and its implications for future research. *Journal of Marketing*, 49(4), 41-50.
- Pattanayak, D., & Maddulety, K. (2018). Effects of tqm on customer satisfaction in indian banking industry: a literature review. *European Journal of Business and Management*. 67(9), 212-220.
- Philip, C. B. (2015). *Quality is still free: making quality certain in uncertain times*, London: McGraw-Hill.
- Pehrsson, N. (2015). Building brands directly: Creating business value from customer Relationships. *Macmillan Business*, 20 (6), 68-82.
- Rachman, A (2017). Analysis of effect of physical evidence and service assurance on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in using car rental service (pt pusaka prima transport cases). iop conf. series: materials science and engineering.
- Sumarjan, N., & Arendt, W. (2016). Quality management implementation in Malaysian hotels: the management perspective. *Middle East Journal of Scientific Research*. 7(4), 619-624